

Why ROR?

**What you should know about the
Research Organization Registry
(ROR)**

Last updated March 6, 2026

What is ROR?

ROR, the Research Organization Registry, is a global, community-led registry of open persistent identifiers for research and funding organizations.

ROR is an established, trusted, widely adopted, no-cost service that is becoming a standard in scholarly communication and scholarly publishing.

Search and browse ROR records at <https://ror.org/search>

Universidade Federal de Santa Maria

ORGANIZATION TYPES

Education, Funder

OTHER NAMES

Labels

Federal University of Santa Maria (en)

Universidad Federal de Santa María (es)

Acronyms

UFSM

LOCATIONS

Santa Maria (GeoNames ID 3450083), Brazil

WEBSITE

<http://site.ufsm.br/>

OTHER IDENTIFIERS

GRID grid.411239.c

ISNI 0000 0001 2284 6531

Crossref Funder ID 501100007337

Wikidata Q3790133

RELATIONSHIPS

Related Organizations

[Hospital Universitário de Santa Maria](#)

Some record data is not displayed in this view. [See JSON view for full record data](#)

Record last modified 2024-05-13. Is there an issue with the data on this record? [Suggest a change](#)

ROR currently includes over 115,000 research organizations from around the world.

All ROR metadata is CC0 and is freely available as JSON & CSV and via a REST API.

The problem: organization name variants

Articles

1-10 of 2232 results for 'Virginia Tech' ←

Select all Export selected citations [Edit search](#) ▾

 Restricted access | Research article | First published Mar 1, 20

[A Digital Library for Recovery, Research, and Learning From April](#)
Edward A. Fox, Christopher Andrews, Weiguo Fan, Jian Jiao, Ananya Kas
Traumatology
[Preview abstract](#) ▾

 Restricted access | Research article | First published Sep 1, 20

[Test Road Experiment on Imminent Warning Rear Lighting and S](#)
Walter W. Wierwille, Suzanne E. Lee, Maryanne C. DeHart, Michael Perel
Human Factors
[Preview abstract](#) ▾

Articles

1-10 of 2899 results for 'Virginia Polytechnic' ←

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 Restricted access | Research article | First published Feb 1, 19

[Reaction Spinning of Polymethylmethacrylate Fibers](#)
Siu Yuen Fok, Richard A. Mickles, Richard G. Griskey
Textile Research Journal
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 Restricted access | Research article | First published Jan 1, 19

[The Effects of the Safe-sun Program on Patrons' and Lifeguards' at Swimming Pools](#)
Richard A. Winett, Bonnie L. Cleaveland, Deborah F. Tate, David N. Lomt
Journal of Health Psychology

ROR solves the problem

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[View all articles by this author](#)

Richard A. Hunt, Ph.D.

ORCID

Name
Richard Hunt

Activities [Collapse all](#)

Employment (2) [Sort](#)

Virginia Tech: Blacksburg, US

2021 to present | Associate Professor (Management)
Employment [Show less detail](#)

Organization identifiers
ROR: <https://ror.org/02smfhw86>
Virginia Tech: Blacksburg, US
<https://www.vt.edu/about/index.html>

Tianzi Wang

ORCID

Activities [Collapse all](#)

Education and qualifications (1) [Sort](#)

Virginia Tech: Blacksburg, Virginia, US

2016 to 2019 | MS (Grado Department of Industrial and Systems Engineering)
Education [Show less detail](#)

Organization identifiers
ROR: <https://ror.org/02smfhw86>
Virginia Tech: Blacksburg, US
<https://www.vt.edu/about/index.html>

History of ROR

<https://ror.org/about/history/>

ROR complements other open identifiers

DOI for research outputs (1997)

ORCID for researchers (2012)

ROR for research organizations (2019)

ROR enables research outputs to be reliably associated with organizations notwithstanding name variants and multilingual names

<https://commons.datacite.org/ror.org/02smfhw86>

ROR makes information better

ROR makes information about research organizations clean, normalized, and easy to exchange among software systems.

Clean information means that journal articles, datasets, and other research outputs can be reliably associated with universities, funders, companies, laboratories, and other institutions.

ROR is free, community-led, and easy

Only ROR offers a free, open, easy, curated, community-led solution that allows research organization metadata to travel between thousands of research systems.

ROR curation is careful, fast, and open

Complete,
accurate,
high-quality
metadata

Responsive
and scalable
request
processing

Transparent
policies,
discussions,
and decisions

ROR update process at a glance

ROR generally publishes new releases twice monthly, meaning that most approved changes appear in ROR no more than 4-6 weeks after the initial request.

ROR has what you need

- 115,000+ records, global coverage
- Open CC0 data and free REST API
- Easy to integrate into software systems
- Multilingual metadata and character sets
- Organization hierarchies and relationships
- Fast, accurate, and transparent curation
- Easy to request changes and additions
- 4-6 weeks to process most requests
- Built-in mapping to other identifiers
- Text to ROR ID matching tools
- Searchable on the web

ROR serves crucial functions

- Collect researcher institutional affiliations
- Standardize and disambiguate organization names
- Enable institutional research intelligence
- Connect funders to the research they have funded
- Make research easier to find
- Manage institutional Open Access deals
- Follow national guidance on open infrastructure
- Improve affiliation metadata in the global research ecosystem

Key systems use ROR

- Core infrastructure services
 - ◆ Crossref
 - ◆ DataCite
 - ◆ ORCID
- Knowledge graphs and large indexes
 - ◆ Web of Science
 - ◆ OpenAlex
 - ◆ Lens
 - ◆ Europe PMC
- Repository and CRIS systems
 - ◆ Dryad
 - ◆ Zenodo
 - ◆ Figshare
 - ◆ DSpace and DSpace-CRIS
- Publishing systems
 - ◆ Open Journal Systems (OJS)
 - ◆ AAAS Science Journals
 - ◆ Scholastica
- ... and more!

<https://ror.org/community/#adopters>

ROR is designed for research workflows

User submits research in a system integrated with ROR

Organization is selected from a ROR-powered controlled list

Shareable metadata includes the ROR ID

Systems use the ROR ID to track research by organization

ROR makes the user experience better

Author(s)

First name *	Last name *	Institutional affiliation: *
<input type="text" value="Amanda"/>	<input type="text" value="French"/>	<input type="text" value="Caltech"/>
		Caltech Submillimeter Observatory (CSO) United States
		California Institute of Technology (CIT) United States
		Recaltech (Brazil) Brazil

Author email *

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4325-1809> Corresponding a

+ Add author

Research domain * Research facility:

Funding

Granting organization: *	Award number	Program/division	remove
<input type="text" value="California Space Grant Consortium"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	

+ Add another funder No funding received

ROR invisibly powers both the "Institutional affiliation" lookup and the "Granting organization" lookup in Dryad.

ROR is noncommercial and sustainable

- ROR is operated as a collaborative initiative by the California Digital Library, Crossref, and DataCite as part of each organization's ongoing operational budget.
- ROR does not depend on grants or on fees, and it cannot be transferred to a commercial entity.
- ROR is committed to following the [Principles of Open Scholarly Infrastructure](#) (POSI).

CDL
California Digital Library

Crossref

DataCite

Do more with ROR!

- Consult our technical documentation at ror.readme.io for help integrating ROR into your own systems
- Ask your colleagues and vendors to adopt ROR
- Share links to this presentation or a 1-page ROR brochure from zenodo.org/communities/ror-community-materials
- Register to attend a ROR event at ror.org/events
- Get involved with the ROR community at ror.org/community#get-involved
- Sign up for the ROR quarterly newsletter at <http://eepurl.com/gjkT9H>

Thank you!
Keep ROR-ing and
keep in touch!

support@ror.org

<https://ror.org>